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**LOCUST BEAN POD SOLUTION (LBPS) AS A NATURAL ADDITIVE FOR IMPROVING THE
STRENGTH CHARACTERISTICS OF NON-LATERITIC SOIL (NLS) SUBGRADE**

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effectiveness of locust bean pod solution (LBPS) as a natural additive for stabilising non-lateritic soil subgrades. The soils strength characteristics were evaluated through California bearing ratio (CBR) and unconfined compressive strength (UCS) tests: the results show that the addition of locust bean pod solution improves the soils strength, with optimal results achieved at 8% solution after 21 days curing. The California bearing ratio values for both soaked and unsoaked conditions ranges from 5.4- 96.35%, exceeding the minimum requirement of 5% for subgrade materials, the unconfined compressive strength value fell within the stipulated range of 750-1500kN/mm² after 7 days of curing. The optimum moisture content and maximum dry density of the stabilised soil were also evaluated with results indicating improved soil density and stability. The study's findings suggest that locust bean pod solution can be used as a sustainable and cost-effective alternative to traditional soil stabilisers. Thus, the use of the locust bean pod solution can potentially reduce the environmental impact and cost associated with soil stabilisation, while improving the strength and stability of non-lateritic soil subgrade. As such, the study recommends further exploration of locust bean pod solution as a viable additive for soil stabilisation in civil engineering applications.

Keywords: Stabilisation, LBPS, Compaction, CBR, UCS and Non-Lateritic Soil

INTRODUCTION

Soil stabilisation is a critical aspect of infrastructural development, with significant implication for road construction and maintainers. Lateritic soils, widely used in subgrades and subbases, often require stabilisation due to their variable geotechnical properties (Nwaiwu *et al.*, 2020). Stabilisers such as lime and cement have been effective but pose environmental and economic challenges (Ayodele *et al.*, 2022). Biopolymer-based stabilisers, particularly Locust Bean Pod solution (LBPS), have emerged as sustainable alternatives (Vordoagu & Adams, 2024).

Cement stabilisation, another widely used technique, enhances soil strength through hydration and the formation of calcium silicate hydrates (Ayodele *et al.*, 2023). This method improves compressive strength, reduces permeability, and increases durability under load-bearing applications (Rahman *et al.*, 2021). However, cement production is a major contributor

to global carbon emissions, necessitating research into alternative binders with lower environmental impact (Basha *et al.*, 2021).

Recent studies have explored the combination of these stabilisers to optimize soil performance while minimizing environmental impact. Hybrid stabilisation approaches, integrating lime, cement, and fly ash, have shown promising results in improving soil properties while reducing the overall quantity of chemical additives required (Jiang *et al.*, 2021). These methods enhance soil load-bearing capacity and durability while addressing cost and environmental concerns.

LBPE has shown potential in improving the compaction characteristics of lateritic soils, increasing Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and reducing Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) (Vordoagu & Adams, 2024; Stephen *et al.* 2025). Research indicates that LBPE stabilises soil by modifying its physical and chemical properties, leading to improved strength and reduced shrinkage. These studies have demonstrated that LBPE-treated lateritic soils exhibit increased unconfined compressive strength (UCS) and California Bearing Ratio (CBR) values, making them suitable for road subgrade stabilisation in conformity with (Osinubi *et al.*, 2022). The stabilising effect of LBPE is attributed to its ability to interact with clay minerals, altering soil plasticity and reducing swelling potential (Ali *et al.*, 2023). Additionally, LBPE enhances soil durability by reducing susceptibility to water-induced erosion and freeze-thaw cycles (Jiang *et al.*, 2021).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The strength characteristics of non- lateritic soil subgrades often pose significant challenges in construction projects, necessitating the use of stabilisation techniques to improve their stability and durability. However, conventional soil stabilisers can be expensive and environmentally hazardous, highlighting the need for sustainable and cost-effective alternatives.

Soil improvement techniques for road construction are used in most parts of world even though the circumstances and reasons for resorting to the technique vary considerably. The researches carried out showed that locust bean pod is a versatile material with unique characteristics, advantages and is being used abundantly all over the world. Therefore, this study has ventured in to a predictive method for the beneficial use of LBPS in harnessing the impending material in the aspect of road construction in term of soil improvement.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The aim of the study is to investigate locust bean pod solution (LBPS) as a natural additive for improving the strength characteristics of non-lateritic soil (NLS) subgrade. The specific objectives are as stated below:

- i. To characterize the Soil and Locust Bean Pod solution (LBPS)
- ii. To investigate the potential of Locust Bean Pod Solution (LBPS) and Cement for stabilisation of Non-Lateritic Soil
- iii. To determine the strength characteristic of the stabilised non-lateritic soil with LBPS.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Materials

a. Soil:

The soil sample collected was via disturbed sampling technique with the aids of digger, shovel and sack, from an existing borrow pit. The soil sample was collected at depths ranging from 1 to 1.2 m. The samples, were collected in sack bags. The sample was air-dried, large lumps crumpled and passed through BS No. 4 sieve (4.75 mm aperture).

b. Locust bean pod solution (LBPS):

Locust bean pod sample was collected from some interior villages in Bali local government area of Taraba state, the sample was collected in large sacks due to its abundant nature around the area and its availability and was transported to the laboratory for the research work.

c. Cement:

The Dangote ordinary Portland cement was obtained from Bali Market

d. Water:

The water used for the research was fetched from the waterworks department

Methodology

This study followed standard testing protocols (BS 1377:1990, ASTM D2487-11 and ASTM D3282-09) for soil testing and oxide composition analysis using XRF. Non-lateritic soil samples were mixed with cement (2% Constant) and locust bean pod solution (0, 2, 4, 6 and 8% by weight of water). Laboratory tests included: Compaction, California Bearing Ratio (CBR) test (soaked and un-soaked conditions) and unconfined compressive strength test. The test evaluated the effects of locust bean pod solution on soil properties.

Compaction Characteristics

The study used British standard light (BSL) and British standard heavy (BSH) compaction technique following BS 1377-1990, to determine the maximum dry density MDD and optimum moisture content OMC of the natural soils and stabilised soil sample. A two phase compaction testing program was conducted: Compaction properties of the untreated natural soil samples which is the phase first and the second phase compaction properties of soil samples stabilised with 2% cement and varying proportions of locust bean pod solution (LBPS) (2, 4, 6 and 8%).

California bearing ratio (CBR)

The tests followed the BS 1377-1990 standard, adopted to suit the requirements in line with Nigerian General specification for Federal Ministry of Works and Housing (FMWH,1997).

Unconfined compressive strength (UCS)

The test procedure followed BS 1924-1990 for natural soil samples. For stabilised soil mixtures, specimens were prepared with 0, 2, 4, 6 and 8% locust bean pod solution (by weight of water), mixture with dry soil and optimal water content determined from moisture- density relationships. Triplicate specimens were prepared for each mix, as per the Nigeria General Specification (FMWH, 1997).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Preliminary test on the Soil

This study presents preliminary test results for natural soil sample and soil samples blended with varying proportions of the locust bean pod solution. The natural soil properties are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Index Properties of the Natural Soil sample

Characteristics	Description
Natural moisture contents (%)	24.1
Liquid Limit (%)	41
Plastic Limit (%)	25.6
Plasticity Index (%)	15.4
Linear shrinkage (%)	13
Percentage passing sieve 200micro	0.39
AASHTO Classification	A-7-6(9)
USCS Classification	SC
MDD (Mg/m ³)	1.93
OMC (%)	11.3
Specific Gravity	2.74
CBR soaked (%)	38.9
CBR un-soaked (%)	96.3
Color	Grey

Chemical properties of the natural soil sample

The summary of the XRF test conducted on the untreated or natural soil obtained have shown that the silica to sesquioxide ratio ratio was greater than 2. This clearly indicates that the soil is non- lateritic in nature. the oxide composition of the soil is shown in table 2.

Table 2: Oxide Composition of the Soil

Oxide	Percentage concentration
SiO ₂	64.092
Fe ₂ O ₃	8.872
Al ₂ O ₃	11.299

Properties of Locust Bean Pod Solution

10kg of the locust bean pod waste was immerse or rather soaked in 25litre of water for a period of 5days with a concentration of 0.4kg/l. The physical and chemical properties of the locust bean pod extract are presented in the table 3.

Table 3. Physical and Chemical properties of LBPE (ASTM C618 - 92a, 1994)

Element	Concentration (%) weight
Color	Dark brown
Tannin Content Concentration	0.061g/ml 400g/l
pH	6.5
Na ₂ O	0.0000
MgO	0.0000
Al ₂ O ₃	0.0000
SiO ₂	45.2203
P ₂ O ₅	0.0000
K ₂ O	33.5274
CaO	14.8564
TiO ₂	1.9126
Fe ₂ O ₃	4.4833

Atterberg limit test conducted

The results obtained from the consistency test showed that the liquid limit content value is 41%, plastic limit 25.6%, linear shrinkage 13 and plasticity index values of 15.4% were obtained for the natural soil. Thus, satisfy the requirement of FMWH (1997) for sub-grade, sub- base and base course material. Thus, the sub-grade material should have $LL \leq 50\%$ and the $PI \leq 30\%$ while for sub-base $LL \leq 30\%$ and $PI \leq 12\%$ respectively.

Compaction Test Results

The compaction tests yielded the maximum dry density(MDD) and optimum moisture content (OMC) for both British Standard Light and British Standard Heavy compaction. The result showed that the MDD and OMC values of $1.73\text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ and 15.9% were obtained for BS L and $1.93\text{mg}/\text{m}^3$ and 11.3% for BSH comp-active effort. It could infer that the higher the comp-active effort the MDD and the lesser the OMC. Similarly, the stabilised soil result showed that the MDD and OMC values of were 1.68, 1.67, 1.64, 1.64 and $1.59\text{Mg}/\text{m}^3$ and 15.9, 16.2, 17.6, 18.4 and 20 % obtained for BSL. And for BSH compactive effort, the MDD and OMC were 1.93, 1.92, 1.92, 1.89 and $1.87\text{Mg}/\text{m}^3$ and 10.25, 10.3, 12.17, 12.40 and 12.70% for the various percentage replacement. As presented in the figures 1 and 2.

Figure 1: Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) BSL

Figure 2: Maximum Dry Density (MDD) and Optimum Moisture Content (OMC) (BSH)

California Bearing Ratio Result for the Tests Conducted

The California Bearing Ratio (CBR) results of Subgrade – locust bean pod extract (LBPE) blends (0, 2, 4, 6 and 8%) ranged from 56.1 to 96.3% and 12.6 to 42.6%, for both un-soaked and soaked conditions as captured in Figures 3

Figure 3: California Bearing Ratio (CBR) BSH

However, subgrade 0% exhibited values of 56.1%, 2, and 4% whose value are 80.7 and 83.3 % for un-soaked conditions, while the blends of 6% LBPE and 8% LBPE exhibited highest CBR values of 96.3% respectively for un-soaked and soaked conditions (control 0%) exhibited CBR value of 12.6% which is the least compared to the blend of 2% cement 2, 4, 6 and 8% blend of LBPE whose values are 18, 26.6 and 31.7 % for the soaked condition similarly 6 and 8% of LBPE exhibited higher values of 38.9 and 42.6% in soaked condition. The trend of the CBR with percentage replacement is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: California Bearing Ratio (CBR) BSL

The CBR value for the controls and the stabilised soil ranged from 8.3 to 38.9% and 9.8 to 29.4% for both un-soaked and soaked conditions. However, it was observed that there was a consistent rise in the CBR value from the control with 2% cement 0% LBPE up to 6 and 8% LBPE with 29.4 and 38.9% higher value. As compared with the other CBR value of 9.4, 19.4, 19.8% and 22% for the case of soaked and for the un-soaked 20.7, 20.9, 28.9 and 29.1%. 6% and 8% LBPE among others give a better CBR result. As stipulation by FMWH (1997) that the un-soaked CBR for subgrade, sub-base and base course material should be $\leq 10\%$, $\leq 30\%$ and $\leq 80\%$ respectively, as all met the requirement for sub-grade.

Unconfined Compressive Strength

As seen in Figure 5, the unconfined compressive strength of cement –treated soil with locust bean pod solution (LBPS) increased with rising locust bean pod solution percentages (0, 2, 4, 6 and 8%) and 2% cement over 21 days curing. This improvement is attributed to the formation of cementitious compounds, which bind the soil particles together, enhancing strength (Fatta *et al*, 2013).

Figure 5: UCS of LBPS-treated non-lateritic soil

The addition of locust bean pod solution to cement-treated soil significantly improved unconfined compressive strength (UCS), increasing with locust bean pod solution concentration and curing time. At 8% locust bean pod solution. Notable UCS values were recorded: 3920, 4040, 4210, 4560 and 4790 KN/m² for 0, 2, 4, 6 and 8% locust bean pod solution, respectively, after 21 days of curing. These results meet the requirements for subgrade and potentially subbase materials for road construction (FMWH, 1997).

CONCLUSION

The following conclusion was drawn:

- i. The soil is non-lateritic in nature and satisfy requirement of a particular class of soil that needs to be stabilised A-7.6 (9) ASHTTO of classification system.
- ii. The compaction test conducted displayed a systemic trend in the decrease in maximum dry density with a corresponding increase in optimum moisture content whose values ranged 1.93 - 1.87Mg/m³, 10.25 - 12.70% for BSH, 15.9 - 20 % and 1.59 - 1.68 Mg/m³ for BSL.
- iii. The California bearing ratio (CBR) for both soak and un-soak condition all satisfied the requirement for subgrade material as in $\leq 10\%$ for subgrade. The values were 9.4 - 22% for the case of soaked and for the un-soaked 20.7 - 29.1% and 56.1 - 96.3% and 12.6 - 42.6% for both light and heavy comp active energy.
- iv. The unconfined compressive strength value ranged from 3920 kN/m² - 4790 kN/m². Thus, it's said that at 6 and 8% replacement, the requirement for subgrade is met.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The locust bean pod extract beyond 8% should be considered to see its effect when its optimum blend is attained.

REFERENCES

- Alfa, U. (2019). *Effect of locust bean pod extract as water reducing admixture on the compressive strength of concrete* [Undergraduate thesis, Kaaf University College].
- Ali, M. H., Rahman, M. M., & Islam, S. (2023). Stabilisation of clay minerals using biopolymer-based additives: A comprehensive review. *Geotechnical Engineering Journal*, 45(3), 234-251.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (1978). *Specifications for pozzolans* (ASTM C618). ASTM International.
- American Society for Testing and Materials. (2003). *Standard practice for classification of soils and soil aggregate mixture for highway construction purpose* (ASTM D3282-09). ASTM International.
- Ayodele, A. L., Olanrewaju, O. A., & Adeyemi, G. O. (2022). Environmental and economic challenges of traditional soil stabilisers in road construction. *Journal of Sustainable Construction Materials*, 8(2), 112-128.
- Ayodele, A. L., Olanrewaju, O. A., & Adeyemi, G. O. (2023). Cement stabilisation techniques: Hydration mechanisms and strength development in tropical soils. *Construction and Building Materials*, 367, 130245.
- Basha, E. A., Hashim, R., Mahmud, H. B., & Muntohar, A. S. (2021). Carbon footprint reduction strategies in cement production: A global perspective. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(15), 18567-18585.
- British Standards Institution. (1990). *Methods of test for soils for civil engineering purposes* (BS 1377). BSI.
- British Standards Institution. (1990). *Stabilised materials for civil engineering purposes* (BS 1924). BSI.
- British Standards Institution. (2000). *Cement: Composition, specifications and conformity criteria for common cements* (BS EN 197-1). BSI Publication.
- Fatta, D., Naoum, F., & Loizidou, M. (2013). Cementitious compounds formation in stabilised soils: Mechanisms and applications. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 25(4), 456-467.
- Federal Ministry of Works and Housing. (1997). *General specification for roads and bridges* (Vol. 2). Federal Highway Department.
- Jiang, Y., Li, J., & Xu, F. (2021). Hybrid stabilisation of problematic soils using lime, cement, and fly ash combinations. *Soil Mechanics and Foundation Engineering*, 58(2), 145-156.
- Nwaiwu, C. M. O., Mezie, E. O., & Aginam, C. H. (2020). Geotechnical properties of lateritic soils and stabilisation requirements for road construction. *Nigerian Journal of Technology*, 39(1), 88-97.
- Osinubi, K. J., Bello, A. A., & Eberemu, A. O. (2022). Potential of biopolymers in soil stabilisation: A review of recent advances. *Geotechnical and Geological Engineering*, 40(3), 1567-1589.
- Rahman, M. M., Gassman, S. L., & Zaman, M. (2021). Engineering properties of cement-stabilised soft clay for sustainable construction. *Journal of Materials in Civil Engineering*, 33(8), 04021195.
- Stephen, C., Umar, S. Y., & Yero, S. A. (2025). Evaluation of Anguwa Sarakuna soil stabilised with cement using locust bean pod solution as sub-grade material for road construction. *Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology Education*, 13(1), 1-15.
- Vordoagu, J. J., & Adams, C. A. (2024). Improvement in compaction characteristics of lateritic gravel soils stabilised with locust bean pod extract. *African Journal of Applied Research*, 10(2), 537-568.

APPENDIX

Plate 1: Compaction test conducted

Plate 2: California bearing ratio test conducted

Plate 3: unconfined compressive strength test conducted